

BLOOMS TAXONOMY IN TEACHING CREATIVE AND CRITICAL THINKING

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Abstract:

Purpose: The study aims to (1) review the literature that analyses the relevance of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives in the teaching of creative and critical thinking among students of TSTU of Almalyk branch and (2) identify missing aspects in Bloom's Taxonomy vis a vis the indigenous context, important to promote creative and critical thinking among students of TSTU of Almalyk branch.

Method: Multiple sources of information which (1) documents the objectives of English Literature curriculum in Malaysia, (2) outlines the nature of Bloom's Taxonomy, (3) reports past research which addresses issues in the application of Bloom's Taxonomy, and (4) reports research findings on the issues in teaching English Literature as a subject.

Significance: The study would shed light on the effectiveness of teaching creative and critical thinking through English Literature. The findings may help curriculum developers and teachers to explore the missing aspects in the Bloom's Taxonomy vis a vis the indigenous context, hence lead to the development of informed way forward in designing effective pedagogical approach/es that nurture creative and critical thinking among students.

Keywords: bloom's taxonomy, taxonomy of learning outcomes, creative thinking, critical thinking, English literature

Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives is a classification system by an educational psychologist, Benjamin Bloom who created it in 1956. The aim was to make students aware of what they were learning, hence striving to attain more sophisticated levels of learning with six cognitive-learning categories. It focuses on developing thinking ability which involves simple information acquisition to more complex processes (Bloom, 1956). Adams (2015) summarizes the six levels of Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive learning objectives as (1) Knowledge, which entails foundational cognitive skill that require students to retain of specific, discrete pieces of information,

(2) Comprehension, which requires students to paraphrase the content of knowledge in their own words, classify items in groups, compare and contrast items with other similar entities, or explain a principle to others, (3) Application, entailing students to use knowledge, skills, or techniques in new situations, (4) Analysis, which requires students to distinguish between fact and opinion and identify the claims upon which an argument is built, (5) Synthesis, which entails the need to create a novel product in a specific situation, and (6) Evaluation, which requires students to critically appraise the validity of a study and judge the relevance of its results for application. The Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives has been regarded for a long time as an important tool for cognitive development. It has influenced many teaching philosophies around the globe especially in promoting rational thinking, often focusing on higher-order thinking skills.

Relevance of the English Literature Subject in the Teaching and Learning of Creative and Critical Thinking Skills In answering a question on whether the Bloom's Taxonomy is relevant to be the bases of learning creative and critical thinking skills in the English literature subject, there are a number of pertinent questions to be attended. First, what is involved in the teaching and learning of English Literature? Do students engage in simple information acquisition or complex thinking processes, the former is a reflection of low order thinking, and the latter for the higher order thinking. The teaching and learning of English Literature fosters creative and critical thinking skills. Defined as the ability to interpret facts, apply generalizations, and recognize errors (D'Angelo, 1970) critical thinking requires students to use content of knowledge that he or she deals with in order to better understand something he or she does not know yet. It also involves the effort to seek for more information that require him or her to ask questions, and come up with the answer of solutions on what he or she was asking for (Elias, 2014).

When teaching literature, the aim is often to nurture thinking. Students should be coached to attempt the reading comprehension questions in order to verify their understanding of the text; learn to detect their weaknesses in logical reasoning; conduct group presentations to enhance their abilities in synthesis, organization, communication and cooperation; be guided in-class discussion with questioning skills to provoke their critical thinking; and be required to attempt individual essay-question reports to promote deductive or inductive reasoning and organization (Tung & Chang, 2009). Teachers' competency in teaching skills in classroom is crucial in order to foster the development of thinking skills among the

students because they can improve their thinking skills if their teachers teach them how to think.

Based on the above, it could be concluded that the teaching of English Literature subject in Almalyk branch TSTU named after I.A.Karimov has a significant attempt to foster creative and critical thinking skills. Nevertheless it is doubtful of whether it involves the required aspects of creative and critical thinking components.

The other issue is on the need to attain higher order thinking skills which reflect students' ability of creative and critical thinking. As such, the teaching and learning of English Literature subject require students to acquire the High Order Thinking Skills. The cognitive abilities to analyses, synthesis, and evaluate have been accorded as the higher order thinking that reflect students' creativity and critical thinking. It was also highlighted that the ability to have critical and creative thinking require students to have more than the cognitive ability but other ability sets such as positive values, befitting the aspiration to develop holistic students. In other word, to be critical is not only to be able to ask and answer questions based on the six domains in the Bloom's Taxonomy.

Conclusion One of the key objectives of education is to develop students' intellectual ability or thinking capacity. Students would be taught creative and critical thinking in certain subjects, including English Literature. This is particularly apt when the assessment of students' learning outcome is based on a taxonomy of learning objectives which focuses on cognitive aspects of learning, the Bloom's Taxonomy. This paper however, argues that the Bloom's Taxonomy of Cognitive Learning is not an appropriate taxonomy to design pedagogical approach for English Literature if we really want to teach creative and critical thinking. There are other criteria which need to be considered and that the whole framework of Bloom's taxonomy may no longer be relevant not only in the Malaysian context but also in the digital age in which pedagogy in teaching literature with digital natives as the targeted group, will need to be reformed.

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